

Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Growth Performance, Carcass Traits, Biochemical Parameters and Immunological Responses of Broiler Chicken

M. Ajafar, A. Alzwghaibi, A. Almamury , M.K.A. Altamimi

Department of Animal Production, College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University, Babylon 51013, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Ajafar, M., Alzwghaibi, A., Almamury, A., & Altamimi, M.K.A. (2024). Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Growth Performance, Carcass Traits, Biochemical Parameters and Immunological Responses of Broiler Chicken. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 371-385.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).31](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).31)

Abstract:

The present study was conducted to investigate effect of shrimp liquid extract on growth performance, carcass traits, immunological responses, and biochemical parameters evaluation of broiler chickens. A total of 360 day-old Ross 308 broiler chicks were randomly allocated to five experimental treatments, with six replicates of 12 birds each. The dietary treatments comprised five different levels (0, 1, 1.5, 2, and 2.5 ml/l) of shrimp liquid extract added to the drinking water of the birds in a completely randomized design over a 35-day trial period. Results showed that supplementation of broiler chickens with different concentrations of shrimp liquid extract, particularly at 2 and 2.5 ml/l, resulted in improved performance metrics. Notably, these concentrations

showed optimal results in terms of carcass yield, weight gain, and organ weights such as breast, thigh, and heart. Serum lipid fractions were not affected by the shrimp liquid extract. However, birds receiving the extract exhibited lower levels of serum creatinine and uric acid, along with higher urea levels. Furthermore, the shrimp liquid extract significantly boosted antibody titers against AIV (Avian Influenza Virus), NDV (Newcastle Disease Virus), IBD (Infectious Bursal Disease) and IBV (Infectious Bronchitis Virus) post-vaccination. Specifically, broilers given 1.5 to 2.5 ml/l of the extract displayed markedly higher antibody titers against various diseases compared to those receiving lower concentrations. Supplementation of shrimp liquid extract in water for broiler chickens at concentrations of 2 and 2.5 ml/l positively impacted performance metrics, organ weights, serum biochemistry parameters, and antibody response against various diseases.

Keywords: Carcass, Drinking water, Extract, Performance, Shrimp liquid.

Introduction

The primary goal of the poultry sector is to attain optimal growth and the most efficient feed conversion rate while ensuring the birds' health is maintained at an optimum level. The present article investigates the potential utilization of amino acids (AA) as nutraceuticals to enhance bird efficiency performance, safeguarding bird health, bolstering immunity, and addressing

various public health concerns. Amino acids have dual roles as building blocks and constituents of proteins. According to nutritional footing, they are divided into two groups: non-essential amino acids, which are built in the body, and essential amino acids that cannot be made by the body at a rate sufficient to maintain metabolic functions. The studies have vindicated the important physiological

roles played by amino acids (AA) in the body (Bortoluzzi et al., 2018; Debnath et al., 2019). Once absorbed, AA enters into assembly and metabolism processes for the synthesis of proteins, applied to the building of different body tissues. The inclusion of AA in poultry nutrition has reduced nitrogen losses during protein metabolism, thereby reducing the excretion of ammonia into the environment, and hence improved performance in broilers (Kidd et al., 2006). The findings of Kidd et al. (2004) Presented above is a table demonstrating that healthy broilers showed positive responses to increased dietary incorporations of Amino acids in diets which had beneficial effects on their performance. Additionally, Beski et al. (2015) reported that supplementing poultry diets with synthetic AA improved feed conversion efficiency and contributed to a reduction in nitrogen excretion.

Recent studies have shown that the bird health status greatly influences amino acid metabolism. The effect of diseases such as necrotic enteritis on AA metabolism could be related more specifically to the interference with digestibility, absorptive capacity, and or even the metabolic capabilities of the said AA. Interestingly, feeding a low protein diet did not increase the chicken's susceptibility to necrotic enteritis although symptoms of the disease were apparent in challenged birds (Hilliar et al., 2020). It is, however, possible to mitigate the effects of this disease by feeding birds a normal diet or better still a diet with an added extra amino acid supplement (Hilliar et al., 2020). Amino acid supplementation sources have been reported to promote cecal butyric acid and total short-chain fatty acid production and hence growth, development, feed conversion efficiency, and immune function improvement (Chrystal et al., 2020; Hilliar et al., 2020).

Dietary amino acid supplementation is vital for optimizing broiler chicken growth and meat yield. The escalating consumer desire for breast fillets and enhanced-value poultry goods has triggered a rising tendency in market weights for broilers (Dozier et al., 2008). AA, particularly lysine, has a pivotal role in muscle growth and optimizing the production of breast meat. The

required lysine level for optimal meat yield may differ from that for increase in body weight and improvement in feed efficiency (Nasr et al., 2011). The interaction between protein and lysine significantly influences the performance and carcass quality of growing chicks. Hence, the dietary protein requirement essentially encompasses the lysine content. Nutritionists have long aimed to enhance growth and tissue development by amplifying the concentration of nutrients, encompassing AA.

Indispensable AA such as methionine, lysine, and threonine play a vital role in enhancing poultry immune function and overall performance (Ojano-Dirain and Waldroup, 2002). Methionine is categorized as the primary limiting amino acid because of its constrained availability in plant-derived protein sources. Its role in feather growth and protein synthesis makes it particularly important in poultry nutrition. In broiler diets, lysine is recognized as the second limiting amino acid, meaning that its availability can restrict the overall protein synthesis. Meanwhile, threonine is the third limiting amino acid, implying that also its inadequate provision could limit the optimal growth and performance of broilers. These AA have pivotal roles in several physiological processes and optimum supplementation is important for proper growth and immune functions in poultry (Shini et al., 2005; Cengiz et al., 2008; Bouyeh, 2013). Si et al. (2001) found that meeting or slightly exceeding the recommended levels of methionine and lysine, as given by the NRC (1994), was a good strategy for enhancing performance in poultry with respect to weight gain and feed conversion. Current research has shown that meeting or slightly surpassing the recommended levels of lysine and methionine according to the NRC (1994) is beneficial for performance in poultry. Some of the studies such as those of Shini et al. (2005), Cengiz et al. It has been demonstrated by several authors that all amino acids, but in particular lysine and methionine, must be increased in the diet to achieve higher breast meat yield in broilers. These authors include Al-Masri et al. (2008), Bouyeh (2013), and Si et al. (2001) who observed that an increase in the

levels of lysine and methionine translates to improved broiler weight gain as well as better feed conversion ratio..

Kidd et al. (2004) conducted on modern commercial broilers (Ross × 508) to evaluate the impact of amino acid levels in optimizing breast meat yield. They emphasized the significance of early-life amino acid intake for maximizing later growth potential. The researchers highlighted the economic benefits of providing higher amino acid levels during the initial growth phase when feed intake is low but growth improvements are substantial. By formulating diets with varying amino acid supplementation levels throughout different feeding phases, they evaluated the subsequent effects on growth performance and carcass yields. The objective of the study was to contribute to the understanding of nutrient management strategies in commercial broiler production.

Materials and Methods

The trial took place at the research poultry field situated within the College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University, in Babil Governorate, to study shrimp liquid extract at different concentrations on the productive performance of broilers Ross 308.

Birds, Housing, Experimental Design and Diet

A total of 360 broiler chickens belonging to the Ross 308 breed were obtained from the Al-Anwar hatchery for the experiment in Al-Kifl district of Babil Governorate. These chickens were divided in a completely randomized design, consisting of five different treatments. Each treatment was replicated six times, with each replicate comprising 12 birds. The treatments

were homogeneous in weights and were placed in 30 pens. Birds were fed during the starter (0-7 days of age), grower (8-14 days of age) and finisher period (15-35 days of age). During the entire duration of the experiment, all birds were provided with unrestricted access to pellet feed and water. In each pen, a single pan feeder and two waterers were provided, while the floor was covered with wood shavings. The lighting schedule followed 21 hours of light and 3 hours of darkness cycle consistently throughout the entire experimental period. The birds and housing facilities underwent three daily inspections and monitoring sessions. The standard diet formulation adhered to the guidelines provided by Ross (Aviagen, 2019). The composition of ingredients and nutrients in the standard diet can be found in Table 1. Transactions are divided into:

- 1- The first group (control) was not given any additives or vitamins.
- 2- The second group was given a solution containing shrimp liquid extract (Table 2) at a concentration of 1 ml per liter of drinking water from the age of one day until the age of 35 days.
- 3- The third group was given a solution containing shrimp liquid extract at a concentration of 1.5 ml per liter of drinking water from the age of one day until the age of 35 days.
- 4- The fourth group was given a solution containing shrimp liquid extract at a concentration of 2 ml per liter of drinking water from the age of one day until the age of 35 days.
- 5- The fifth group was given a solution containing shrimp liquid extract at a concentration of 2.5 ml per liter of drinking water from the age of 35 days.

Table 1. The Formulation and Computed Analysis of Standard Diets

Ingredient%	Starter (0-7 d)	Grower (8-14 d)	Finisher (15-35 d)
Corn	39.43	43.01	47.40
Soya meal (44%)	44.35	40.10	34.65
Wheat	10	10	10
Concentrate ¹	2.5	2.5	2.5
Calcium carbonate	1.27	1.06	1.26

Sunflower oil	2.28	3.16	4.07
Salt (NaCl)	0.17	0.17	0.17
Sum	100	100	100
Composition analysis			
ME (kcal/Kg)	3000	3.100	3.200
Crude protein%	23	21.5	19.5
Ca%	0.96	0.87	0.79
Available P%	0.48	0.43	0.39
Na%	0.16	0.16	0.16
Lysine%	1.44	1.29	1.15
Methionine%	0.77	0.70	0.64
Threonine%	0.97	0.88	0.78
Met + Cys%	1.08	0.99	0.90
DCAB ² (mEq kg ⁻¹)	236	220	200
Crude fiber %	5.05	4.84	4.55
Fat%	3.10	3.08	3.04
Linoleic acid%	1.02	1.09	1.17

Note: ¹Provime concentrate produced by Provime / Dutch: Jordanian origin Each kg contains: 17% crude protein, 1.5% crude fat, 1% fiber, 14% calcium, 6.7% available phosphorus, 4.8% sodium, 5.8% chloride, 13.7% total phosphorus, 9.3% non-lysine, 7.8% methionine + cysteine, 0.4% tryptophan, 2100kcal/kg energy representative, 480000 IU vitamin A, 220000 IU vitamin D3, 3000 mg Vitamin E, 138 mg Vitamin K3, 138 mg Vitamin B1, 280 mg Vitamin B2, 600 mg Vitamin B5, 48 mg Vitamin B6, 1000 mg Vitamin B9, 1800 mg Niacin, 6900 mg Biotin, 2400 mg Iron, 3500 mg Zinc, 3200 mg Manganese, 480 mg Copper, 10 mg Selenium, 48 mg Iodine, 250 mg Antioxidant. (2) According to each of the energy represented, crude protein, crude fiber, fat, lysine, and methionine + cysteine calcium, and bio phosphorus. Note. ME: metabolizable energy. ²DCAB = Na + K – Cl.

Table 2. Chemical Analysis of Shrimp Liquid Extract Dietary Supplement in

No	Nutrients	Concentrate
1	Protein (min)	18%
2	Digestible Protein (min)	16%
3	Moisture (max)	10%
4	Methionine	0.046 (mg)
5	Lysine	0.095 (mg)
6	Glutamic Acid	0.233 (mg)
7	Aspartic Acid	0.147 (mg)

Each chick was individually weighed, and at the conclusion of each phase, both the feed and the broiler were weighed to determine BW (body weight), BWG (body weight gain), FI (feed intake) and FCR (feed conversion ratio). The FCR was computed by dividing the total FI by the corresponding BWG. The experiment used shrimp liquid extract from (Vietnam Food Joint Stock Company) which consists of the following

materials (total protein 18%, digested protein 16%, methionine 0.046 mg, lysine 0.095 mg, glutamic acid 0.233 mg, and aspartic acid 0.147 mg) and imported by Babylon Land Paradise Company. It holds a quality certificate from the General Veterinary Company in Iraq. The company's recommendations for the prescribed dose for use were 1 ml/liter of drinking water, and the dose was increased according to the experiment parameters mentioned above.

Carcass Traits

On the 35th day of the trials, six chicks from every treatment type were killed following an overnight fast to assess carcass yield and characteristics. Carcass weight was measured post-evisceration, and the heart, liver, gizzard, breast, and thigh were extracted from the carcass and weighed.

Biochemical Parameters Evaluation

One chick was randomly chosen from each replicate at the conclusion of the experiment, blood serum parameters were analyzed to assess the physiological indicators. Blood samples were gathered in tubes without heparin for biochemical analyses. After collection, all tubes were kept at 25°C for 15 minutes of centrifugation at 3000 rpm to separate out serum from other components. The separated serum samples so obtained were kept in deep freezer at -20°C and analyzed further for albumin by colorimetric method using standard commercial kits procured from Bio lab A.S., France. Whereas the blood biochemistry profile including creatinine, urea and uric acid were assessed by using enzymatic kits from Bio System, Spain, the blood serum levels of cholesterol and triglycerides along with the HDL levels and VLDL's in the serum were determined following Zangana et al al. (2008), using commercial kits purchased from bio system, Spain. HDL and VLDL in serum were estimated by method of Dong et al al (2015).

Immunological Responses

At the ages of 10, 13, 15, and 18 days, the broilers were vaccinated against IBV, NDV, AIV, and IBD viruses. Blood samples were collected on

days 6 and 12 post-NDV and AIV vaccination, day 10 post-IBV, and IBD vaccination from the hens for rational evaluation for antibody response for various viral antigens. Anti-NDV and anti-AIV antibody response was determined by hemagglutination inhibition test (Jahanian, 2009), methods described by Moghaddam and Jahanian (2009). However, ELISA was used for detection of anti-IBV or anti-IBD response.

Statistical Analysis

The dataset underwent a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS version 9.1 software. To assess significant differences, a significance level of 5% was employed, and Duncan's multiple range test was conducted.

Results

Growth Performance

The results of the growth performance experiment are outlined in Table 3. The results demonstrate that the supplementation of different concentrations of shrimp liquid extract improved the performance of broiler chickens ($P \leq 0.05$). Notably, the optimal performance was observed at the concentrations of 2 and 2.5 ml/l of the shrimp liquid extract ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 3. Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Growth Performance of Broiler Chickens on 1-35 d. (math. Mean \pm standard error)

Treatments	BW, g	FI, g	BWG, g	FCR, g/g
0	2058.33 \pm 8.33 c	3898.00 \pm 36.51 d	1894.00 \pm 35.67 c	2.06 \pm 0.05 a
1	2316.67 \pm 83.33 b	4105.67 \pm 17.38 c	2254.33 \pm 90.26 b	1.82 \pm 0.07 b
1.5	2333.33 \pm 44.09 b	4178.67 \pm 14.44 bc	2331.67 \pm 44.33 b	1.79 \pm 0.03 b
2	2550.00 \pm 86.60 a	4237.33 \pm 3.75 b	2732.67 \pm 103.76 a	1.55 \pm 0.05 c
2.5	2566.67 \pm 66.66 a	4379.33 \pm 49.65 a	2789.33 \pm 79.88 a	1.57 \pm 0.02 c
Significance level	**	**	**	**

Note: ^{a-c} A significant difference exists between means that are accompanied by distinct superscripts ($P \leq 0.05$); *Significant at 95% ($p \leq 0.05$); ** significant at 99% ($p < 0.01$); ¹Body weight (BW) body weight gain (BWG), feed intake (FI), and feed conversion ratio (FCR).

Carcass Traits

Table 4 illustrates the impact of treatments on carcass traits of broilers. Treatments exerted an influence on carcass yield, breast, thigh, and

heart parameters. The inclusion of 2.5 ml/l of shrimp liquid extract resulted in the highest weight gain ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 4. Effects of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Characteristics of Carcass (g) of Broilers at 35 d (math. Mean \pm standard error)

Treatments	Carcass, g	Breast, g	Thigh, g	Liver, g	Heart, g	Gizzard, g
0	1688.33 \pm 71.66 b	850.01 \pm 50.01b	666.66 \pm 33.33 b	40.66 \pm 2.18	9.00 \pm 1.52 b	40.00 \pm 1.73
1	1631.67 \pm 51.34 b	816.66 \pm 16.66 b	650.00 \pm 28.86 b	38.33 \pm 0.88	10.33 \pm 0.88 b	44.33 \pm 5.20
1.5	1696.67 \pm 61.93 b	866.66 \pm 16.66 b	700.00 \pm 28.86 ab	41.33 \pm 3.33	11.66 \pm 1.66 ab	39.66 \pm 2.60
2	1763.33 \pm 51.34 b	883.33 \pm 33.33 b	733.33 \pm 33.33 ab	37.66 \pm 1.33	11.66 \pm 0.33 ab	39.60 \pm 0.33
2.5	2050.00 \pm 28.86 a	1016.67 \pm 16.66a	800.00 \pm 28.86 a	44.66 \pm 3.71	14.33 \pm 0.66 a	39.33 \pm 2.33
Significance level	**	**	**	NS	**	NS

Note: ^{a-b} A significant difference exists between means that are accompanied by distinct superscripts ($P \leq 0.05$); *Significant at 95% ($p \leq 0.05$); ** significant at 99% ($p < 0.01$); NS = non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

Biochemical Parameters

Serum Lipid Profile

The results presented in Table 5 showed that the effect of shrimp liquid extract did not affect the

serum lipid fractions of 35-day-old broiler chickens ($P > 0.05$).

Table 5. Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Serum Lipid Profile¹ of Broiler Chicken of 35 d (math. Mean \pm standard error)

Treatments	Cholesterol (mg/100ml)	Triglyceride (mg/100ml)	HDL (mg/100ml)	LDL (mg/100ml)	VLDL (mg/100ml)
0	73.33 \pm 4.63	108.00 \pm 18.90	73.33 \pm 4.63	108.16 \pm 16.19	38.00 \pm 11.23
1	197.00 \pm 24.00	196.66 \pm 53.73	67.66 \pm 9.93	111.34 \pm 33.30	22.33 \pm 4.17
1.5	163.33 \pm 34.64	126.00 \pm 14.15	70.33 \pm 10.13	111.32 \pm 23.41	23.66 \pm 4.09
2	191.66 \pm 30.55	191.66 \pm 30.55	82.66 \pm 0.33	87.38 \pm 28.80	21.33 \pm 2.027
2.5	141.33 \pm 12.77	106.00 \pm 2.64	70.00 \pm 8.88	50.03 \pm 3.53	21.00 \pm 0.57
Significance level	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Note: ¹HDL (high-density lipoproteins), LDL (low-density lipoproteins) and VLDL (Very-low-density lipoproteins); NS = non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

Serum Metabolites

Table 6 indicates that broilers fed shrimp liquid extract in water significantly had lower levels of

serum creatinine and uric acid, and higher urea levels, in comparison with the control birds ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 6. Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Serum Creatinine, Uric acid, Urea and Albumin of Broiler Chickens (Means \pm standard error)

Treatments	Creatinine (mg/dl)	Uric acid (mg/dl)	Urea (mg/dl)	Albumin (g/dl)
0	0.66 \pm 0.13 a	7.40 \pm 0.05 a	3.10 \pm 0.26 b	2.41 \pm 0.10
1	0.66 \pm 0.13 a	7.20 \pm 0.15 ab	3.38 \pm 0.13ab	2.45 \pm 0.13
1.5	0.36 \pm 0.03ab	6.366 \pm 0.79 ab	3.46 \pm 0.43ab	2.68 \pm 0.04
2	0.40 \pm 0.10ab	6.26 \pm 0.20 ab	3.66 \pm 0.23ab	2.48 \pm 0.24

2.5	0.33± 0.06 b	6.06± 0.08 b	4.04±0.16 a	2.22± 0.14
Significance level	**	**	**	NS

Note: ^{a-b} A significant difference exists between means that are accompanied by distinct superscripts ($P \leq 0.05$); *Significant at 95% ($p \leq 0.05$); ** significant at 99% ($p < 0.01$); NS = non-significant ($p > 0.05$).

Immunological Responses

The effect of shrimp liquid extract was highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$) on the titer of antibodies for AIV, NDV, IBD and IBV at 6, 10 and 12 post-vaccination (Table 7). The groups of broilers fed shrimp liquid extract at 1.5 to 2.5 ml/l had significantly higher antibody titers against AIV,

NDV, IBD and IBV than the other groups fed 0 and 1 ml/l of the shrimp liquid extract, at different periods post-vaccination ($P \leq 0.05$). Consequently, it could be suggested that the humoral immune response to NDV, AIV, and IBV was triggered subsequent to vaccination in the broilers supplemented with the higher doses of shrimp liquid extract.

Table 7. Effect of Shrimp Liquid Extract on Antibodies Titer (Ab) Against Viral Diseases AIV, NDV, IBD and IBV¹ at Periods Post Vaccination (math. Mean ± standard error)

Treatments	AIV (\log_2)	NDV (\log_2)	IBD (\log_{10})	IBV (\log_{10})
0	11.66 ± 0.66c	5.69 ± 0.49 c	4.003 ± 0.70 d	3.09 ± 0.29 d
1	12.00 ± 1.00 c	8.65 ± 1.23 b	5.72 ± 0.13 cd	3.85 ± 0.34 cd
1.5	30.33 ± 5.45bc	10.37 ± 0.46 ab	6.21 ± 0.26 bc	5.18 ± 0.38 bc
2	38.33 ± 4.63 b	12.33 ± 1.16 a	7.853 ± 0.48 b	6.13 ± 0.09 b
2.5	70.33 ± 11.09 a	13.77 ± 0.43 a	1.51 ± 0.88 a	8.44 ± 0.79 a
Significance level	**	**	**	**

Note: ^{a-c} A significant difference exists between means that are accompanied by distinct superscripts ($P \leq 0.05$); *Significant at 95% ($p \leq 0.05$); ** significant at 99% ($p < 0.01$); ¹Infectious bronchitis (IBV), Newcastle disease virus (NDV), avian influenza virus (AIV), and infectious bursal disease (IBD).

Discussion

Growth Performance

Shrimp liquid extract supplementation at concentrations of 2 and 2.5 ml/l significantly improved the performance of broiler chickens in the growth performance experiment. Dozier et al. (2007) found that Broilers were provided with diets formulated to have a high amino acid (AA) density experienced reduced FI and improved FCR compared to broilers that were assigned diets with a moderate AA density during the 42-56-day period of age. Dozier et al. (2008) reviewed the literature on the density of dietary AA and its impact on broiler performance and meat yield. Their findings indicated the formulation of diets with higher AA density in commercial broiler production has been

observed to result in reduced FI and improved FCR. Also, other researchers (Almamury et al., 2021) reported that dietary NBS herbal supplements containing crude protein improves growth performance in broiler chickens. Kidd et al. (2005) found that high amino acid density diets increased diet costs but decreased feed costs per kilogram of BW or carcass at day 35. Feed costs per kilogram of BW increased at day 55 due to more phases of high amino acid diets. broilers fed all high amino acid diets had higher income over feed costs per bird at both 35 and 55 days compared to birds fed all medium amino acid diets. Their results highlight the importance of meeting amino acid needs in high-yield broilers for maximizing profitability (Kidd et al., 2005). Recent studies have indeed demonstrated that increasing the dietary protein levels, specifically by enhancing the amino acid density

in broiler diets, can lead to improvements in both the FCR and breast meat yield (Kidd et al., 2004; Corzo et al., 2010). This has been observed in different genetic strains and across various stages of broiler development. Implementing high amino acid density diets in the starter phase, despite lower feed intake, can lead to greater economic returns (Kidd et al., 2004), with benefits carrying over to market age (Halevy et al., 2000; Pophal et al., 2004). Additionally, increasing essential AA levels, such as lysine, in the finisher diet improves FCR and breast meat yield compared to diets with average AA densities commonly used in the United States (Dozier et al., 2007). Optimizing AA levels in broiler diets enhances growth performance and economic profitability (Vieira and Angel, 2012).

According to Gouz and Morris (2005), fast-growing broilers experience a faster increase in amino acid requirements compared to energy requirements. As a result, these strains require a higher dietary ratio of AA to energy. In the experiment conducted by Vieira et al. (2004), it was found that the cockerels achieved their maximum weight gain and protein content on diets with significantly lower protein substances compared to what was required to maximize the gain in the broilers. Also, On the other hand, it is important to consider some of the possible disadvantages. According to Cowieson et al. (2005), extreme heating conditioning can result in the inactivation of vitamins and a decrease in amino acid availability due to the Maillard reaction. Consequently, the utilization of protein supplements contains some of AA, such as shrimp liquid extract in water, can enhance the performance of broilers.

Carcass Traits

The inclusion of 2.5 ml/l shrimp liquid extract gave the highest weight gain. Hence, dietary lysine should be increased from 100% to 112% NRC (1994) within a protein source that strictly limits amino acid after balancing for arginine. These are to be done while maintaining the isotentricity and 112% NRC levels of methionine within the diet. The effect of the dilysine interaction had been noted by Dozier et al. (2008). They reported that optimum results

could be obtained by maintaining the diet at a ratio equivalent to lysine /threonine of 1.5:1; i.e., broilers attained maximum body weight gain and optimal fillet, drumstick and thigh yields at 150% and 100% of NRC recommendations for lysine and threonine, respectively (Dozier et al., 2008).

Vieira et al. (2004) have documented that augmenting the levels of total sulfur AA can lead to elevated returns in relation to breast meat yield or carcass yield. Moreover, these responses are influenced by the genetic characteristics of the broilers. Kidd et al. (2005) reported that broilers fed diets with high amino acid density showed improvements in various parameters including 35 and 55 days carcass weight, fillet weight, tender weight, tender yield, total breast weight, total breast yield, drumstick weight, saddle weight, and wing weight. As a result, they assumed incorporating a high amino acid density diet in each phase led to increased diet costs. However, despite the increase in diet cost, when expressed as feed costs per kilogram of BW or weight of carcass at day 35, there was a decrease.

Alfaro-Wisaquillo et al. (2021) found that increasing the dietary lysine level to 110% during the rearing phase resulted in higher breast meat yield and decreased abdominal fat yield in pullets at 20 weeks of age. Pullets that were fed the 110% lysine diet exhibited a higher percentage of over-fleshed birds compared to those on diets with lower lysine content (80%, 90%, and 100%). These results not only emphasize the importance of adding AA during the early stages of broiler development but also highlight the potential economic benefits of meeting or exceeding the amino acid requirements through the use of shrimp liquid extract in water for high-yield broilers.

Biochemical Parameters

Serum Lipid Profile

Shrimp liquid extract had no significant effect on serum lipid fractions in 35-day-old broiler chickens. Azzam and El-Gohary (2015) confirmed these results by observing that increasing the dietary levels of Threonine (0.76% and 0.79%) resulted in non-significant elevations in plasma cholesterol concentrations compared to the standard level recommended by the NRC

(0.74%). In line with our experiment, the findings of El-Katcha et al. (2018) revealed that the supplementation of AA, specifically lysine, methionine and threonine at a level exceeding the recommended dose (30% excess) in the diet of Cobb chicks, resulted in a non-significant elevation in the concentrations of blood serum triglycerides, cholesterol, and HDL after 42 days of age and conversely, Lysine supplementation exhibited a non-significant reduction in blood serum LDL (low-density lipoproteins) concentration and contributed to a decrease in the TCHO/HDL ratio compared to the control group.

Lysine supplementation in broiler diets can lead to higher serum cholesterol levels. This may be due to Lysine's role as a precursor for L-carnitine, which promotes fatty acid oxidation and reduces adipose tissue storage. Lysine also stimulates insulin secretion from the pancreas in poultry, which, unlike in mammals, can have a glucagon-like effect, releasing fatty acids and AA and promoting protein synthesis (Sturkie et al., 1986).

Serum Metabolites

Shrimp liquid extract supplementation in broilers' water resulted in lower serum creatinine and uric acid levels, as well as higher urea levels. Arginine, considered a functional amino acid, goes beyond its primary role in protein synthesis and serves various secondary metabolic functions. It acts as a precursor for several important compounds, including NO (nitric oxide), proline, hydroxyproline, polyamines, glutamine, ornithine, and creatine (Wu et al., 2009; Castro and Kim, 2020). Notably, creatine and phosphocreatine play vital roles in maintaining cellular energy homeostasis. Guanidinoacetate, a critical component in creatine synthesis, is formed from the interaction of arginine and cysteine. The interactions and dietary responses involving arginine, cysteine, and guanidinoacetic acid have been extensively examined and reviewed by Portocarero and Braun (2021).

Gong et al. (2005) have established that serum levels of creatinine and uric acid can serve as reliable indicators of protein and amino acid

metabolism. It is widely recognized, as highlighted by Namroud et al. (2008) that the absorption rate of synthetic AA surpasses that of intact proteins. Some recent studies have also revealed that inclusion in diets with artificial amino acids is related to the lowest plasma uric acid content; for example, this has been shown by Ospina-Rojas et al. (2014) and Min et al. (2017). Arginine supplementation helps maintain a high level of creatine under conditions when birds are provided with an arginine-deficient diet. The reason lies in the involvement of arginine in the synthesis of precursors to creatine where birds are inefficient in producing arginine as Chamruspollert et al., (2002) observed. Arginine-deficient basal diets affected the growth performance of broilers negatively, resulting in abnormalities in creatine and phosphocreatine levels in muscle tissue, as demonstrated by DeGroot et al. (2018). Supplementation of the arginine-deficient diet with 0.16% and 0.32% L-arginine led to a corresponding increase in creatine and phosphocreatine levels in the muscle tissue of broilers (Oliveira et al., 2022). It thus underscores the importance of L-arginine supplementation for the maintenance of proper creatine metabolism in broilers.

During amino acid catabolism, every amino acid has to lose its amino terminus. This is important because nitrogenous compounds do not enter into the energy transduction pathways. Furthermore, high accumulations of amino groups could be highly toxic Namroud et al. ; Zarghi et al., 2020a. Consequently, the uremic-blood levels of uric acid (UA) should serve as an index of Amino Acid utilization in the body. The higher concentration of UA in blood means less Nitrogen is being retained in the body, and more possibilities exist for Ammonia excretion. Blood serum UA levels can reveal the Amino Acid Utilization in Broilers provided with either adequate or marginal levels of dietary Protein (Zarghi et al., 2020a; Zarghi et al., 2020b). Analysis depicted that UA in blood serum of broiler chickens showed quadratic mode of change versus varying levels of dietary sulfur amino acids and from this average pattern, the highest concentration is related to birds fed

0.86% digestible sulfur AA diet which also depict the lowest level as per related study by Ghavi et al., (2020). Similar to our findings, Powell et al. (2009) reported that incorporation of glycine (2.32% glycine + serine) caused a decrease in serum uric acid as well as serum urea nitrogen levels in broilers at 18 days of age. This is in line with our findings. Additionally, their conclusion stated that the addition of glycine resulted in a decrease in serum uric acid levels in diets containing 1.35% lysine and excessive total sulfur AA. They reported that one possible mechanism for this effect is an increase in cysteine formation. The broiler's cysteine requirement is within the range suggested by previous studies (Kalinowski et al., 2003; Baker, 2005). However, the synthesis of cysteine from glycine and methionine may utilize energy that could be used for growth. Inadequate synthesis of cysteine can lead to the accumulation of methionine precursors, negatively impacting growth performance (Powell et al., 2009).

Immunological Responses

Shrimp extract increased antibody levels in broilers post-vaccination, with higher doses showing greater enhancement. The health condition of fowls may be determined by the strength of their immune system. Essential amino acids play an important role in the production of cytokine and immune function and, therefore, are important reservoirs (Kidd, 2004; Li et al., 2007). It would seem that the demand for essential AA would increase with immune stress or inflammation (Le Floc'h et al., 2004). They also contribute to antibody production in animals (Han and Lee, 2000). Reasonable intake with feed of dietary amino acids is able to make an important contribution towards the normal immune reaction as well as defense against a variety of diseases across species diversity (Beski et al., 2015). Thus, it would be prudent to say that providing a diet with sufficient levels of amino acids could boost the development of their immune function.

The history of amino acid requirements in broiler chickens has been traditionally related to their position in protein structure. Specific amino acids have been recognized as playing

critical regulatory roles in gene expression, intracellular protein turnover, nutrient metabolism, immune responsiveness, and oxidative defense upon multicellular organisms, as gauges and fine-tuners of such biological processes (Wu, 2010; Yu et al., 2022). Chrystal et al. (2020) and Hilliar et al. (2020) noted that amino acid supplementation favors enhancing immune function.

Most essential of the amino acids present in animal cells is the amino acid Arginine, specially indispensable for fast-growing animals such as broiler and pigs. The functional activities of this amino acid include detoxification of ammonia, protein synthesis, and immunomodulatory mediation as well as a nutrient metabolism immune functions, and hormone secretion particularly those of growth hormones. Metabolism and its products, such as nitric oxide, and polyamines have an influence on immune regulation as well as the activation of T cell's. According to studies, dietary deficiency of arginine in broilers causes a significant decrease in the weight of both the thymus and spleen. This deficiency also results in the decrease in heterophil proportion in peripheral blood, and antibody titer against NDV (Moghaddam & Jahanian, 2009). Arginine holds promise as an immunomodulatory agent that enhances immunologic functions in broilers. (Xu et al., 2018). Furthermore, arginine has been shown to boost the specific immune response against IBD in chickens (Tayade et al., 2006).

Bird's performance studies have proved that immunity can be improved by methionine and threonine in the diet. Threonine is a proteinogenic amino acid. Methionine enhances antibody levels in the blood or production of other kinds of immune factors in birds (Azzam, and El-Gogary, 2015; Trevisi et al., 2015). Several reports also consist that threonine supplementation above the NRC (1994) while meeting the requirement promotes better growth, gut health, and increased immunity (Ahmad et al., 2020). El-Katcha et al. (2018) Lysine, Methionine, and Threonine supplementation and combinations all increased broiler chicks' antibody titers at day 35 and 42.

Methionine supplementation improves antibody production in broiler chicks. It is an essential amino acid involved in protein synthesis, glutathione production for cell protection, synthesis of polyamines for cellular processes, and DNA methylation. Adequate levels of methionine and lysine are necessary for optimal immune system function (Bouyeh, 2012). Supplemental lysine or methionine has been found to enhance the immune responses of broilers (Faluyi et al., 2015; Saleh et al., 2018). The administration of lysine and methionine treatments at levels 30% and 40% higher than the NRC, (1994) recommendations, respectively, led to a notable reduction in heterophils and a surge in blood lymphocytes. This also led to a shift in the heterophils-to-lymphocytes ratio, serving as an index for stress (Bouyeh, 2012).

Glutamine is recognized for its role in supplying nitrogen and serving as an energy source for the growth of immune and intestinal mucosal cells. It is essential in conjunction with cysteine for the synthesis of antioxidants like glutathione (Newsholme, 2001; Obled, 2003). Wang et al. (2013) extensively elucidated the functional roles of glycine, which encompass antioxidative capacity, enhanced immunity, facilitation of wound healing, and reinforcement of gut integrity.

Tryptophan, when used as a supplement, serves a dual purpose: it is essential for protein synthesis and acts as a precursor to serotonin, a neurotransmitter that plays a key role in regulating feed intake (Kerr et al., 2005).

Conclusion

Supplementation of shrimp liquid extract in water at concentrations of 2 and 2.5 ml/l had positive effects on performance metrics, organ weights and health in broiler chickens.

Disclosure Statement

The author(s) of the study reported no potential conflict of interest.

Funding

No Funding

Author Contributions

Majeed Ajafar: conceptualisation; funding acquisition; methodology; supervision, validation.

Ayyed Alzwghaibi: conceptualisation & editing; supervision, validation, methodology.

Ali Almamury: Correspondence, conceptualisation; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project administration; resources; software; writing – original draft; writing – review & editing; Visualization.

Mohammed k.A. Altamimi: conceptualisation & editing; supervision.

References

- Ahmed, I., Qaisrani, S. N., Azam, F., Pasha, T. N., Bibi, F., Naveed, S., & Murtaza, S. (2020). Interactive effects of threonine levels and protein source on growth performance and carcass traits, gut morphology, ileal digestibility of protein and amino acids, and immunity in broilers. *Poultry Science*, *99*(1), 280–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2019.09.034>
- Alfaro-Wisaquillo, M. C., Oviedo-Rondón, E. O., Cordova-Noboa, H. A., Caldas, J. V., Quintana-Ospina, G. A., Ospina-Rojas, I. C., & San Martin, V. (2021). Effects of amino acid levels during rearing on Cobb 500 slow-feathering broiler breeders: 1. Growth and development. *Poultry Science*, *100*(9), 101327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2021.101327>
- Almamury, A., Hassanabadi, A., Zerehdaran, S., & Nassiri-Moghaddam, H. (2021). Effects of dietary supplementation of a herbal product (NBS Superfood) on growth performance, intestinal morphology, immune status, and blood metabolites in broiler chickens. *Poultry Science Journal*, *9*(2), 245–254.

- Aviagen. (2019). Ross broiler: Nutrition specification. Huntsville, AL: Aviagen. Retrieved from <https://www.aviagen.com>
- Azzam, M. M. M., & El-Gogary, M. R. (2015). Effects of dietary threonine levels and stocking density on the performance, metabolic status, and immunity of broiler chickens. *Asian Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 10(5), 215–225. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ajava.2015.215.225>
- Baker, D. H. (2005). Comparative nutrition and metabolism: Explication of open questions with emphasis on protein and amino acids. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(50), 17897–17902. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0508837102>
- Beski, S. S., Swick, R. A., & Iji, P. A. (2015). Specialized protein products in broiler chicken nutrition: A review. *Animal Nutrition*, 1(2), 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2015.05.001>
- Birmani, M. W., Raza, A., Nawab, A., Tang, S., Ghani, M. W., Li, G., & An, L. (2019). Importance of arginine as an immune regulator in animal nutrition. *International Journal of Veterinary Science*, 5(1), 1–10.
- Bortoluzzi, C., Rochell, S. J., & Applegate, T. J. (2018). Threonine, arginine, and glutamine: Influences on intestinal physiology, immunology, and microbiology in broilers. *Poultry Science*, 97(3), 937–945. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pe425>
- Bouyeh, M. (2012). Effect of excess lysine and methionine on immune system and performance of broilers. *Annals of Biological Research*, 3(7), 3218–3224.
- Castro, F. L. S., Kim, Y., Xu, H., & Kim, W. K. (2020). The effect of total sulfur amino acid levels on growth performance and bone metabolism in pullets under heat stress. *Poultry Science*, 99(11), 5783–5791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.08.002>
- Cengiz, O., Onol, A. G., Sevim, O., Ozturk, M., Sari, M., & Daskiran, M. (2008). Influence of excessive lysine and/or methionine supplementation on growth performance and carcass traits in broiler chicks. *Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire*, 159(4), 230–236.
- Chamruspollert, M., Pesti, G. M., & Bakalli, R. I. (2002). Dietary interrelationships among arginine, methionine, and lysine in young broiler chicks. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 88(6), 655–660. <https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN2002738>
- Chrystal, P. V., Moss, A. F., Khoddami, A., Naranjo, V. D., Selle, P. H., & Liu, S. Y. (2020). Effects of reduced crude protein levels, dietary electrolyte balance, and energy density on the performance of broiler chickens offered maize-based diets with evaluations of starch, protein, and amino acid metabolism. *Poultry Science*, 99(3), 1421–1431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2019.10.038>
- Corzo, A., Schilling, M. W., Loar, II R. E., Mejia, L., Barbosa, L. C. G. S., & Kidd, M. T. (2010). Responses of Cobb×Cobb 500 broilers to dietary amino acid density regimens. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 19(3), 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.3382/japr.2010-00156>
- Cowieson, A. J., Hruby, M., & Faurschou Isaksen, M. (2005). The effect of conditioning temperature and exogenous xylanase addition on the viscosity of wheat-based diets and the performance of broiler chickens. *British Poultry Science*, 46(6), 717–724. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071660500303414>
- Debnath, B. C., Biswas, P., & Roy, B. (2019). The effects of supplemental threonine on performance, carcass characteristics, immune response, and gut health of broilers in subtropics during pre-starter and starter period. *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition*, 103(1), 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.12972>
- DeGroot, A. A., Braun, U., & Dilger, R. N. (2018). Efficacy of guanidinoacetic acid on growth and muscle energy metabolism in broiler chicks receiving arginine-deficient diets. *Poultry Science*, 97(3), 890–900. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pe425>
- Dong, J. Q., Zhang, H., Jiang, X. F., Wang, S. Z., Du, Z. Q., Wang, Z. P., & Li, H. (2015). Comparison of serum biochemical parameters between two broiler chicken lines divergently selected for abdominal fat content. *Journal of*

Animal Science, 93(7), 3278–3286.
<https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2014-8908>

Dozier, III W. A., Corzo, A., Kidd, M. T., & Branton, S. L. (2007). Dietary apparent metabolizable energy and amino acid density effects on growth and carcass traits of heavy broilers. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 16(2), 192–205.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/16.2.192>

Dozier, III, W. A., Kidd, M. T., & Corzo, A. (2008). Dietary amino acid responses of broiler chickens. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 17(1), 157–167. <https://doi.org/10.3382/japr.2007-00066>

El-Katcha, M. I., Soltan, M. A., El-Shall, N. A., & El-Desoky, A. M. (2018). Effect of high dietary level of some amino acids and coccidial infection on growth performance and health status of broiler chicken. *Alexandria Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 58(1), 112–120.
<https://doi.org/10.5455/ajvs.256423>

Faluyi, O. B., Agbede, J. O., & Adebayo, I. A. (2015). Growth performance and immunological response to Newcastle disease vaccinations of broiler chickens fed lysine supplemented diets. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Health*, 7(3), 77–84.
<https://doi.org/10.5897/JVMAH2014.0325>

Ghavi, S., Zarghi, H., & Golian, A. (2020). Effect of dietary digestible sulphur amino acids level on growth performance, blood metabolites, and liver functional enzymes of broilers 1–11 days of age. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, 19(1), 1439–1449.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1828051X.2020.1834567>

Gong, L. M., Lai, C. H., Qiao, S., Li, D., Ma, Y. X., & Liu, Y. L. (2005). Growth performance, carcass characteristics, nutrient digestibility, and serum biochemical parameters of broilers fed low-protein diets supplemented with various ratios of threonine to lysine. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 18(8), 1164–1170.
<https://doi.org/10.5713/ajas.2005.1164>

Gous, R. M., & Morris, T. R. (2005). Nutritional interventions in alleviating the effects of high temperatures in broiler production. *World's*

Poultry Science Journal, 61(3), 463–475.
<https://doi.org/10.1079/WPS200570>

Halevy, O., Geyra, A., Barak, M., Uni, Z., & Sklan, D. (2000). Early posthatch starvation decreases satellite cell proliferation and skeletal muscle growth in chicks. *Journal of Nutrition*, 130(4), 858–864.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/130.4.858>

Han, I. K., & Lee, J. H. (2000). The role of synthetic amino acids in monogastric animal production—A review. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 13(4), 543–560.
<https://doi.org/10.5713/ajas.2000.543>

Hilliar, M., Keerqin, C., Girish, C. K., Barekatin, R., Wu, S. B., & Swick, R. A. (2020). Reducing protein and supplementing crystalline amino acids to alter dietary amino acid profiles in birds challenged for subclinical necrotic enteritis. *Poultry Science*, 99(4), 2048–2060.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2019.11.027>

Jahanian, R. (2009). Immunological responses as affected by dietary protein and arginine concentrations in starting broiler chicks. *Poultry Science*, 88(8), 1818–1824.
<https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2008-00425>

Kalinowski, A., Moran Jr, E. T., & Wyatt, C. (2003). Methionine and cystine requirements of slow- and fast-feathering male broilers from zero to three weeks of age. *Poultry Science*, 82(9), 1423–1427. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/82.9.1423>

Kerr, B. J., Moran Jr, E. T., & Kidd, M. T. (2005). Effect of supplementary tryptophan prior to marketing on carcass quality in broilers. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 14(2), 306–314.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/14.2.306>

Kidd, M. T. (2004). Nutritional modulation of immune function in broilers. *Poultry Science*, 83(4), 650–657. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/83.4.650>

Kidd, M. T., Corzo, A., Hoehler, D., Miller, E. R., & Dozier, W. A. III (2005). Broiler responsiveness (Ross × 708) to diets varying in amino acid density. *Poultry Science*, 84(9), 1389–1396. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/84.9.1389>

Kidd, M. T., McDaniel, C. D., Branton, S. L., Miller, E. R., Boren, B. B., & Fancher, B. I. (2004). Increasing amino acid density improves

- live performance and carcass yields of commercial broilers. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 13(4), 593–604. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/13.4.593>
- Kidd, T., Corzo, A., & Branton, S. L. (2006). Growth and meat yield and economic responses of broilers provided three- and four-phase regimens formulated to moderate and high nutrient density during a 56-day production period. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 15(3), 315–325. <https://doi.org/10.1093/japr/15.3.315>
- Le Floch, N., Melchior, D., & Obled, C. (2004). Modifications of protein and amino acid metabolism during inflammation and immune system activation. *Livestock Production Science*, 87(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livprodsci.2003.09.005>
- Li, P., Yin, Y. L., Li, D., Kim, S. W., & Wu, G. (2007). Amino acids and immune function. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 98(2), 237–252. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S000711450769936X>
- Min, Y. N., Liu, S. G., Qu, Z. X., Meng, G. H., & Gao, Y. P. (2017). Effects of dietary threonine levels on growth performance, serum biochemical indexes, antioxidant capacities, and gut morphology in broiler chickens. *Poultry Science*, 96(5), 1290–1297. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pew447>
- Moghaddam, H. N., & Jahanian, R. (2009). Immunological responses of broiler chicks can be modulated by dietary supplementation of zinc-methionine in place of inorganic zinc sources. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 22(3), 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.5713/ajas.2009.80613>
- Namroud, N. F., Shivazad, M., & Zaghari, M. (2008). Effects of fortifying low crude protein diet with crystalline amino acids on performance, blood ammonia level, and excreta characteristics of broiler chicks. *Poultry Science*, 87(11), 2250–2258. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2008-00121>
- Nasr, J., & Kheiri, F. (2011). Increasing amino acids density improves broiler live weight. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 10(7), 523–526. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ijps.2011.523.526>
- National Research Council, & Subcommittee on Poultry Nutrition. (1994). *Nutrient requirements of poultry*. National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/2114>
- Newsholme, P. (2001). Why is L-glutamine metabolism important to cells of the immune system in health, postinjury, surgery, or infection? *Journal of Nutrition*, 131(9), 2515S–2522S. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jn/131.9.2515S>
- Obled, C. (2002). Amino acid requirements in inflammatory states. *Canadian Journal of Animal Science*, 82(1), 55–66. <https://doi.org/10.4141/A01-067>
- Ojano-Dirain, C. P., & Waldroup, P. W. (2002). Evaluation of lysine, methionine, and threonine needs of broilers three to six weeks of age under moderate temperature stress. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 1(1), 16–21. [https://doi.org/10.3923/ijps.2002.16.21​3::contentReference\[oaicite:0\]{index=0}​3::contentReference\[oaicite:1\]{index=1}](https://doi.org/10.3923/ijps.2002.16.21​3::contentReference[oaicite:0]{index=0}​3::contentReference[oaicite:1]{index=1})
- Oliveira, C. H., Dias, K. M., Bernardes, R. D., Diana, T. F., Rodrigues, R. J., Calderano, A. A., & Albino, L. F. (2022). The effects of arginine supplementation through different ratios of arginine: lysine on performance, skin quality, and creatine levels of broiler chickens fed diets reduced in protein content. *Poultry Science*, 101(11), 102148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.102148>
- Ospina-Rojas, I. C., Murakami, A. E., Duarte, C. R. A., Eyng, C., Oliveira, C. A. L., & Janeiro, V. (2014). Valine, isoleucine, arginine, and glycine supplementation of low-protein diets for broiler chickens during the starter and grower phases. *British Poultry Science*, 55(6), 766–773. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2014.967202>
- Pophal, S., Vieira, S. L., Kessler, A. M., Ebert, A. R., & Gallo, B. B. (2004). Broiler growth in response to increased lysine in the first week post-hatching. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 87(Suppl. 1), 267. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(04\)70033-6](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(04)70033-6)

- Portocarero, N., & Braun, U. (2021). The physiological role of guanidinoacetic acid and its relationship with arginine in broiler chickens. *Poultry Science*, *100*(7), 101203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2021.101203>
- Powell, S., Bidner, T. D., & Southern, L. L. (2009). The interactive effects of glycine, total sulfur amino acids, and lysine supplementation to corn-soybean meal diets on growth performance and serum uric acid and urea concentrations in broilers. *Poultry Science*, *88*(7), 1407–1412. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2008-00510>
- Saleh, A. A., Ragab, M. M., Ahmed, E. A., Abudabos, A. M., & Ebeid, T. A. (2018). Effect of dietary zinc-methionine supplementation on growth performance, nutrient utilization, antioxidative properties, and immune response in broiler chickens under high ambient temperature. *Journal of Applied Animal Research*, *46*(1), 820–827. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09712119.2018.1479694>
- Shini, S., Li, X., & Bryden, W. L. (2005). Methionine requirement and cell-mediated immunity in chicks. *Asia Pacific Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, *14*(Suppl. S), S123.
- Si, J., Fritts, C. A., Burnham, D. J., & Waldroup, P. W. (2001). Relationship of dietary lysine level to the concentration of all essential amino acids in broiler diets. *Poultry Science*, *80*(10), 1472–1479. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/80.10.1472>
- Sturkie, P. D. (1986). *Avian Physiology* (4th ed.). Springer-Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-4862-0>
- Tayade, C., Jaiswal, T. N., Mishra, S. C., & Koti, M. (2006). L-Arginine stimulates immune response in chickens immunized with intermediate plus strain of infectious bursal disease vaccine. *Vaccine*, *24*(5), 552–560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2005.08.076>
- Trevisi, P., Corrent, E., Mazzoni, M., Messori, S., Priori, D., Gherpelli, Y., & Bosi, P. (2015). Effect of added dietary threonine on growth performance, health, immunity, and gastrointestinal function of weaning pigs with differing genetic susceptibility to *Escherichia coli* infection and challenged with *E. coli* K88ac. *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition*, *99*(3), 511–520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.12262>
- Vieira, S. L., & Angel, C. R. (2012). Optimizing broiler performance using different amino acid density diets: What are the limits? *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, *21*(1), 149–155. <https://doi.org/10.3382/japr.2011-00492>
- Vieira, S. L., Lemme, A., Goldenberg, D. B., & Brugalli, I. (2004). Responses of growing broilers to diets with increased sulfur amino acids to lysine ratios at two dietary protein levels. *Poultry Science*, *83*(8), 1307–1313. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/83.8.1307>
- Wang, W., Wu, Z., Dai, Z., Yang, Y., Wang, J., & Wu, G. (2013). Glycine metabolism in animals and humans: Implications for nutrition and health. *Amino Acids*, *45*(3), 463–477. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-013-1493-1>